

standICT.eu²⁰²⁶

ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Policy Paper

The Evolving ICT Standardisation Landscape

Europe's Role and
Impending Questions

Credits

Main author - Astor Nummelin Carlberg (Executive Director of OpenForum Europe)

Contributors - Knut Blind (Head of Business Unit Innovation and Regulation at Fraunhofer ISI), Francesco Osimanti (Senior Project Manager at Trust-IT)

Design - Gianluca Savini (Trust-IT)

Legal notice

The document has been prepared for the European Commission and SDOs however it reflects the views only of the authors, and neither the European Commission nor the Standards Developing organisations can be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein. More information on the European Union is available on the internet (<http://europa.eu>).

About StandICT.eu

The [StandICT.eu](#) 2026 Coordination and Support Action project is funded by the European Union under grant agreement no. 101091933. The project is coordinated by [Trust-IT Srl](#) (IT) in quality of Technical Coordinator and [Dublin City University](#) (IE) in quality of Financial Coordinator, supported by the partners [European Digital SME Alliance](#) (BE), [OpenForum Europe](#) (BE), [Australo](#) (ES) and [Fraunhofer ISI](#) (DE). The content of the present report does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

■ Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	2
Introduction and Background.....	3
StandICT.eu 2026.....	4
Research Questions.....	5
Definitions and Limits for the Study.....	6
Approaches to a broad definition of the ICT standardisation landscape.....	6
Approach chosen for the upcoming study.....	8
Thematic Areas and Case Studies.....	9
Change 1: The digital markets are being regulated.....	9
Change 2: Geopolitical rivalries politicise standardisation.....	10
Change 3: The number of technology areas being ‘standardised’ outside of the traditional system is increasing.....	10
Research Design.....	12
Data Collection.....	12
Case studies.....	12
Potential Implications of the Research Findings.....	13

■ Executive Summary

The Information and Communication Technology (ICT) standardisation landscape is transforming, and Europe is both a driver of and affected by change. This policy paper, authored by OpenForum Europe experts and supported by the StandICT.eu 2026 consortium, outlines our upcoming research intent and focus when exploring the evolving ICT standardisation landscape. The paper also argues for the comprehensive approach we have adopted for our research, integrating views from diverse stakeholders, organisations, and policies to offer a complete perspective. Input for this interim publication is based on ten on-background interviews with experts in the field.

The policy paper highlights the three key thematic areas of change, and the subsequent hypotheses, that our coming research project will analyse:

Digital Market Regulations

The digital domain is experiencing profound regulatory shifts, which have direct and indirect effects on the standardisation landscape. Governments are transitioning from interoperability to compliance, increasingly likely to embed specifications in legislation. Influenced by liability challenges, product liability law variations, and administrative urgency, there's a tilt from licensing to liability resulting from the regulation of the software market.

Politicisation of Standardisation

Politics is increasingly entwined with technical standardisation. Countries are formulating their standardisation blueprints, spotlighting critical technologies. The narratives now integrate ethics, often viewed politically. There's a perceived change in the geographies that hold strategic standard essential patents, raising concerns and potential external pressure on standardisation bodies.

Evolving 'Standardisation' Outside Traditional Systems

Standardisation governance has increased in complexity, and this development is not slowing. Alternative platforms like fora and consortia are also increasingly playing an important role. Large corporations use APIs to steer tech and market directions. The trend towards royalty-free standards is evident, as well as open source development. In a time of fast technological change, this poses challenges for traditional standards development organisations (SDOs). The traditional SDOs grapple with merging open source approaches with established intellectual property norms.

We aim to assist policymakers and stakeholders with our upcoming research insights, and if possible amplify public comprehension of ICT standardisation. Feedback on this initial paper is welcomed for a thorough topic exploration.

■ Introduction and Background

This policy brief seeks to outline our intent and focus when exploring the evolving ICT standardisation landscape and its subsequent implications for the European Union (EU). The final report, *'Europe's Role in an Evolving ICT Standardisation Landscape'* will present a comprehensive analysis spanning three thematic areas, delve into six case studies, and proffer a set of policy recommendations for the European Commission. The policy note is the result of ten on-background interviews with experts in the field, which in turn have supported us in refining and shaping the research design and focus of the upcoming study.

To enhance our comprehension of the shifting ICT standardisation landscape, we will adopt a comprehensive approach that encompasses a broad spectrum of stakeholders, organisations, interests, laws, policies, and judicial decisions. This methodology is rooted in our commitment to offering a holistic perspective, ensuring that no crucial details are overlooked. That said, when adopting such a holistic approach, detailed exactness will ultimately suffer. This is a trade off that we believe we have to make in order to meet the research challenge. We hope, however, that it will yield a different and complementary view on current developments in this space.

When mapping the ICT standardisation landscape, we have discerned four different approaches, in terms of describing the terrain: 1) "What standardises?"; 2) The Legal Landscape; 3) Stakeholders; and 4) Organisations and Institutions. For this study, we will integrate all four, which will guide the formulation of our questionnaire and the selection of interviewees. Through our questionnaire, we hope to comprehend the intricate nature of standardisation, appreciating both its core role in the ICT sector and the various factors that shape its future.

Ultimately, the objective of our research is to identify the shifts that significantly affect stakeholders, alter legal frameworks, and influence the principal actors in the ICT standardisation domain.

The task to explore the evolving landscape of ICT standardisation and its implications for Europe is an ambitious undertaking. In order to shape the research, we incorporated a methodological approach that involved conducting "on-background" interviews of experts in the field. It is the findings of these interviews that are presented in this paper. This two-stage approach was deemed essential to ensure that the research design was both robust and aligned with the current trends and challenges in the field.

We sought to engage with experts who are renowned for their comprehensive understanding and are considered "big thinkers" in the realm of ICT standardisation. A total of 10 experts were identified and approached.

The experts consulted included:

- ▷ A specialist from a leading global technology company specialising in visual computing and AI solutions.
- ▷ An economist specialising in standardisation and software.
- ▷ An expert from a prominent open source foundation known for its collaborative projects and initiatives.
- ▷ An authority from a project focused on supply chain standards.
- ▷ An authority from an international consortium dedicated to ensuring the open development and evolution of standards.
- ▷ A professional from a global organisation advocating for open source software and its communities.
- ▷ A professional from a multinational technology company with a history in computer hardware, software, and services.
- ▷ An expert from a small standards consultancy with small and medium-sized software companies as clients.
- ▷ An expert from a major digital technology association representing the digital technology industry in Europe.
- ▷ A specialist from an initiative dedicated to promoting open standards and practices.

A cornerstone of the on-background interview process was the assurance of confidentiality. Participants were informed that their contributions would be treated with the highest level of discretion. Specifically, no direct attributions will be made to any individual participant in this or any subsequent reports or publications. This measure was instituted to encourage open and candid discussions, ensuring that the insights gleaned were both genuine and uninhibited.

Note that this shapes how this policy paper should be read. The statements and assertions made in this document are to be tested by upcoming qualitative and quantitative research. For this preliminary report, we find this approach acceptable. The future research publication will be fully referenced.

■ StandICT.eu 2026

This research is being conducted in the context of StandICT.eu 2026. This project aims to further its impact and reach within the European ICT Standardisation Ecosystem. The project's primary objectives include:

1. Launching and managing a robust and efficient facility supporting the Fellowship Programme;
2. EUOS (EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation) and Technical Working Groups (TWGs) empowering contributions from ICT standardisation experts;
3. Training the next generation of ICT standardisation experts, engaging with National Standardisation Bodies and PPPs through the Standards Education Group (EUOS-SEG);
4. Ensuring high-level steering of StandICT.eu 2026 by means of an authoritative Expert Group (the EAG) who tap directly into the WGs & TCs of SDOs, tackling EU priorities, challenges and gaps;
5. Creating an engaging & influential Forum on EU Strategy for ICT standards to address policy (FOREST), to keep momentum in policy discussions, in-synch with the MSP and subsequent high-level forum to be rolled-out in 2022.

The project is coordinated by Trust-IT Srl (IT) and is a collaborative effort with five partners: Dublin City University (IE), OpenForum Europe (BE), AUSTRALO (ES), European Digital SME Alliance (BE), and Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research ISI (DE).

■ Research Questions

With our large scope in mind, the following research questions were defined:

- ▷ RQ1: What are the major internal changes that affect the ICT standardisation landscape?
- ▷ RQ2: What are the major external changes that affect the ICT standardisation landscape?
- ▷ RQ3: How do these changes impact the various stakeholders within the landscape?
- ▷ RQ4: What are the repercussions of these changes on the different organisations and institutions operating within the landscape?

Explanation of terms

Internal change:

A modification or transformation originating from within an entity, system, or process, often driven by factors such as organisational culture, policies, capacity building or operational shifts.

External change:

A modification or transformation that is influenced or triggered by factors outside the entity, system, or process, such as market trends, regulatory changes, legal rulings or external events.

Stakeholder:

An individual, group, or organisation that has a vested interest in a particular project, decision, or outcome and can be affected by or can affect its success.

Organisation and institutions:

Entities at different levels of formality that have a structured system for achieving a set of goals or purposes; where “organisation” refers to entities like businesses or nonprofits, and “institutions” refer to longstanding societal structures or establishments like governmental bodies.

■ Definitions and Limits for the Study

While opting for a broad definition might compromise precision, our aspiration is to encompass the macro and external factors that are driving change in ICT standardisation. This will enable us to discern how these external pressures interplay with the internal dynamics of organisations and stakeholders traditionally associated with the ICT standardisation landscape.

Approaches to a broad definition of the ICT standardisation landscape

The task of delineating this vast expanse is pivotal, influencing everything from our research design to the manner in which we address our research queries. We have four approaches to this end:

- ▷ **Approach 1:** “What standardises?”;
- ▷ **Approach 2:** The Legal Landscape;
- ▷ **Approach 3:** Stakeholders; and
- ▷ **Approach 4:** Organisations and Institutions.

For the study, we have opted to combine all these approaches for a very broad definition.

Approach 1: “What standardises?”

In our quest to understand the intricacies of standardisation, we must first grapple with a seemingly simple question: what standardises? This question asks us to go beyond the confines of formal institutions and consider the broader set of influences that shape the ICT landscape. An initial dichotomy is what is colloquially called *de facto* and *de jure* standards. Historically, ‘*de facto* standards’ have emerged, overshadowing formal standardisation. These arise when a technology or service becomes an informal industry or societal benchmark.

Looking beyond the formal definitions that usually make up the foundation for research in this field, we will want to make sure to include and further understand the role of:

- ▷ **Open Source and its Influence:** The open source realm seemingly runs parallel to formal standardisation. This dynamic world sees standards as popular software projects or practices that, while not official, wield significant influence.
- ▷ **APIs of Large Companies in Concentrated Markets:** Dominant tech firms’ APIs can set *de facto* standards in digital markets. In such concentrated arenas, these APIs guide third-party integrations, shaping competition and innovation dynamics.
- ▷ **Formal Standardisation and Fora and Consortia:** Europe’s standardisation landscape is enriched by entities like ETSI, CEN, and CENELEC. Industry-led consortia and fora, while complementing these bodies, add layers of complexity to the region’s standardisation approach.
- ▷ **The Interplay of Standardisation in Different Regions of the World:** Different regions adopt varied standardisation approaches. And the standards they adopt will influence the standards adopted elsewhere.

Approach 2: The Legal Landscape

Beyond technological developments and organisations, standardisation is sculpted by laws and regulations. Governments contribute their perspective and interests defining the legal landscape(s) for standardisation. The legal underpinnings of standardisation form a sometimes labyrinthine matrix, reflecting the complexities of the ICT sector and the many jurisdictions it spans.

- ▶ **International Frameworks:** At the global level, instruments like the WTO Rules on Standardisation and the Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) rules provide overarching guidelines, setting the tone for national and regional regulations.
- ▶ **Regional Strategies and Regulations:** Each major geopolitical entity, from the US and EU to China, has in recent years crafted its bespoke standardisation strategy. These strategies, while rooted in global principles, reflect regional priorities, challenges, and ambitions. Strategies include the EU Standardisation Strategy and the United States Government National Standards Strategy for Critical and Emerging Technology. These complement already established regulations, such as the Regulation 1025, the New Approach and the NLF in the EU, and harder policy tools such as the White House Entity List in the US.
- ▶ **Emerging Legal Influences:** Regulation of technologies will have different effects on the standardisation landscape. New regulations, such as the Digital Markets Act and Digital Services Act, will have effects on what is being standardised and also how.

Approach 3: Stakeholders

The standardisation process involves a diverse array of stakeholders, from end-users and consumers to engineers, developers, and policymakers. We will try to outline the changes in the roles and relationships between these different entities, and how they interact and influence each other in the standardisation landscape. Their collective contributions are instrumental in shaping the trajectory and outcomes of standardisation.

1. End Users:

- ▶ **Business Users and Consumers:** The primary beneficiaries of standardisation, their preferences and feedback are crucial in ensuring that standards are user-centric and address real-world needs (B2B and B2C perspectives).
- ▶ **Citizens:** Ultimately, standards serve the wider public interest and not just niche or commercial interests. This arguably drives government interest in the space.

2. Technical Experts:

- ▶ **Engineers and Developers:** The technical architects behind the technologies, they provide the foundational knowledge and expertise that underpin the creation and refinement of standards.
- ▶ **Standards Experts and Professionals:** These individuals possess deep expertise in the intricacies of standardisation processes, methodologies, and best practices. They often act as bridges between technical developers and policy makers.

3. Academic and Research Community:

- ▶ **Academics and Researchers of Standardisation:** Their insights and research findings offer a theoretical lens through which the process and impact of standardisation can be critically examined.
- ▶ **Academics and Researchers of the Actual Technologies:** By studying the technologies themselves, they provide a deeper understanding of their functionalities, potentialities, and limitations.

4. Advocacy and Civil Interests:

- ▶ **Civil Society Organisations:** Advocates for societal interests, working to ensure that standards are developed with broader societal implications in mind, from environmental sustainability to social equity.

5. Policy and Regulation:

- ▶ **Policy Makers:** Their regulatory frameworks and policies can mandate, influence, or be influenced by standards, ensuring alignment with national or regional objectives.

6. Business and Commercial Interests:

- ▶ **Companies:** Be they users or providers of digital products and services, companies' commercial interests and market strategies drive the need for new standards or the revision of existing ones.
- ▶ **Telecom Operators:** As the backbone of communication infrastructures, their operational needs and challenges are central to many ICT standards.
- ▶ **Start-ups and SMEs:** Their unique challenges and needs are considered by policymakers who want to make sure that standards are inclusive and don't disproportionately favour larger entities.
- ▶ **Investors:** Their financial backing and strategic interests can influence the direction and priorities of standardisation, especially in emerging tech domains.

Approach 4: Organisations and Institutions

We will also look into the organisations and institutions that are involved in creating, implementing, and maintaining standards, as well as entities that are outside of the actual standards process, which perhaps create reference implementations, policy and regulation, or translate between the different entities.

- ▶ **Formally recognised SDOs:** Standard Development Organisations (SDOs) are the bedrock of the ICT standardisation landscape. Renowned institutions such as ITU, ISO JTC 1, CEN, CEN-CENELEC, and ETSI are at the forefront of crafting, implementing, and preserving standards that shape the digital realm. Additionally, National Standards Bodies contribute significantly in this domain.
- ▶ **Fora, Consortia, and Specialised Entities:** The standardisation arena is augmented by a diverse array of fora, consortia, and specialised entities. Organisations like ICANN, IETF, 3GPP, and GSMA bring specialised expertise to the table. Additionally, emerging market SDOs, including TSDSI in India, TTA in Korea, and ARIB in Japan, provide essential regional insights.
- ▶ **Open Source Entities:** Open source initiatives predominantly reside within dedicated foundations and projects, such as the Linux, Apache, and Eclipse Foundations. These entities not only focus on reference implementations of standards but are increasingly involved in formal standard creation. The Joint Development Foundation under LF is an interesting example blurring the lines.
- ▶ **Civil Society and Industry Collaborations:** Civil society organisations, in tandem with industry consortia, are focused on the broader spectrum of societal needs linked to standards. Entities like the Digital SME Alliance, ANEC, and BEUC underscore this commitment.
- ▶ **Middleware Organisations:** Middleware organisations act as intermediaries in the standardisation landscape, bridging potential divides and fostering dialogue amongst varied stakeholders. There are entities that are set up by the government as well, as seen in the Multi-Stakeholder Platform on ICT Standardisation and the newly established European Union High Level Forum on Standardisation. Non-government entities in this category include the Digital SME Alliance and OpenForum Europe.

■ Approach chosen for the upcoming study

To deepen our understanding of the evolving ICT standardisation landscape, we've chosen a comprehensive approach that includes a wide array of stakeholders, organisations, interests, laws, policies, and court cases. This approach stems from our dedication to providing a broad view.

In other words, we'll incorporate all four previously discussed approaches, which will steer the development of our research design and our selection of interview participants. Ultimately, our study's goal is to pinpoint the macro shifts that have a notable effect on stakeholders, change legal structures, and impact the key players in the ICT standardisation arena.

■ Thematic Areas and Case Studies

The thematic areas have been, and the case studies will be, chosen based on their relevance to the current ICT landscape and their potential impact on Europe. The criteria for selection prioritise areas that indicate significant change and have far-reaching consequences for standardisation practices.

Change 1: The digital markets are being regulated

The landscape of digital markets is undergoing significant changes due to new regulations, in particular in the EU. These changes are not only introducing fresh standardisation requests into the system but also bringing in new stakeholders who expect to be acknowledged and, in some cases, actively involved. One notable trend is the manner in which governments are now directly incorporating specifications into their legal frameworks. This practice might alter the focus of standards bodies and professionals. Moreover, such decisions, if made without comprehensive community engagement, can result in regulations that might not adequately address the multifaceted nature of the digital world, and challenges the open governance model promoted by most standards bodies, fora and consortia.

Another discernible change is that, historically, there has been an emphasis on interoperability, but now there's a marked shift towards ensuring compliance in digital markets in areas such as cyber security, content moderation or accessibility. This transition is further intensified by the intricate challenges surrounding liability and the often pressing expectations on governments. The old dependence on the evolution of commercial law is now facing scrutiny, with governments adopting a more directive stance.

In the realm of commercial law, there's a clear trend moving from licensing to a focus on liability and contract. The intricacies of product liability law, particularly when it comes to software, is also expected to create drastic changes.

Possible Case Studies

- ▶ The European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
- ▶ The EU's approach to regulating AI and its implications for standardisation
- ▶ The Cyber Resilience Act and its implications for standardisation

Change 2: Geopolitical rivalries politicise standardisation

The domain of technical standardisation has been undergoing a profound shift, increasingly veering into the realm of politics. Or is politics veering into the realm of standardisation? This politicisation is evident as nations craft their own standardisation strategies, signalling a departure from purely technical considerations. Central to these strategies are lists of critical technologies, which indicate the strategic interests and priorities of a country. Alongside this, there's an emphasis on infusing ethics and values into the standardisation discourse, which might not be intended as political, but can be perceived that way. It's worth noting that the invocation of "ethics" isn't always a prerequisite for justifying a government's strategic directions.

Amid these developments, there's a sentiment in the industry that the holders of strategic Standard Essential Patents (SEPs) are evolving. This perceived 'changing of guard' has given rise to apprehensions about governance and the potential for undue influence from third countries over standardisation bodies. Such concerns aren't limited to high-profile entities but extend to technical bodies across the spectrum of formality.

Possible Case Studies

- ▷ Global tech rivalry and its implications for 5G standardisation
- ▷ The European Union's push for digital sovereignty and its impact on tech standards
- ▷ The global standardisation battle over facial recognition technology

Change 3: The number of technology areas being 'standardised' outside of the traditional system is increasing

On the one hand, governance mechanisms overseeing standardisation are undergoing changes, becoming more intricate. This complexity arises just as there's a pressing need to streamline and expedite processes, ensuring they remain in step with the speed of technological advancements. The urgency of this adaptation is further underscored by a growing call for transparency. Smaller companies, in particular, often find themselves navigating a challenging terrain, where the system's intricacy is compounded by its lack of clarity.

Amidst these shifts, alternative standardisation platforms, such as fora and consortia, are now established in the standardisation arena. On another front, the very large digital companies are not merely passive observers. They are also actively shaping the future, using, for example, their Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) as powerful tools to dictate both technological trajectories and market dynamics. This proactive stance by very large corporations is juxtaposed against the challenges faced by Standard Development Organisations (SDOs). Their once-reliable business models now seem vulnerable, especially in light of changing market appetites and the relentless march of technology.

One of the most palpable shifts in this space is the gravitation towards royalty-free standards. These standards, favoured for their cost-effectiveness and devoid of royalty burdens, which in turn enables open source development, are being embraced at an unprecedented rate. The ripple effects of this trend are evident in the ICT standardisation system, especially at the de jure level, which is inundated with these royalty-free standards.

Traditional stalwarts like ISO, ITU, IEC, DIN, and ETSI are actively grappling with these challenges. A challenge that is increasingly pronounced is these entities' attempts to champion open source initiatives. The world of open source, with its ethos of sharing and version control, presents a paradigm shift. While resting on a strong intellectual property foundation, the open source approach is unconventional compared to standardisation, which has historically been anchored in the realm of tangible, finite assets. As the modern economy increasingly celebrates the sharing ethos and intangible assets that can be replicated *ad infinitum*, traditional entities are at a crossroads, trying to reconcile the open source philosophy with traditional intellectual property frameworks.

Possible Case Studies

- ▶ The Open Compute Project in standardising data centre technologies
- ▶ The influence of major corporations like Amazon and Microsoft in shaping cloud standards
- ▶ The rise of royalty-free video codecs and their impact on the multimedia industry

■ Research Design

■ Data Collection

For data collection for this ambitious research scope, the research team has set a sample size of 30 interviews. The selection criteria for these interviews are based on the expertise of the participants and on a desire to ensure a diverse representation in terms of geography and gender. We plan to include five policymakers, ten standards professionals, ten experts from companies specialising in standards, and five alternative experts who can provide insights for specific case studies or offer alternative viewpoints on the subject.

■ Case studies

The data for the case studies will be gathered through a blend of desk research and interviews. Specific interviews may be conducted for certain case studies to validate the data collected. This will not be the bulk of the research, as the thematic areas of change will be the focus. The case studies are meant to illustrate the points put forward with a practical example.

Selection criteria for case studies

1. **Relevance to Research Objectives** - The case should be directly related to the shifts in the ICT standardisation landscape and its implications for the European Union (EU).
2. **Availability of Data** - The feasibility of collecting comprehensive data for the case should be considered. Cases with limited or inaccessible data might not provide the depth required for the study.
3. **Significance of Impact** - Cases that have led to significant changes in the landscape should be prioritised.
4. **Diversity of Perspectives** - Cases should represent a mix of internal and external changes, different stakeholders, and various organisations and institutions.
5. **Temporal Relevance** - Cases should be recent enough to provide insights into the current landscape of ICT standardisation. However, historical cases that offer significant lessons or contrasts can also be considered.

Potential Implications of the Research Findings

The changing landscape of ICT standardisation has implications for policymakers, stakeholders, and the general public. As the research team explores this area, several potential outcomes and considerations are hoped for:

For Policymakers:

- ▶ **Strategic Decision-making:** The research team hopes to offer insights to guide policymakers in their decisions about ICT standardisation, ensuring Europe's continued relevance in technology.
- ▶ **Regulatory Frameworks:** The findings may suggest areas where current regulations could be updated or where new regulations might be needed to address the evolving dynamics of ICT standardisation.

For Standardisation Stakeholders:

- ▶ **Adaptation to Change:** Stakeholders, from tech giants to startups, may benefit from understanding the shifts in the standardisation landscape, allowing them to adapt their strategies accordingly.
- ▶ **Collaboration Opportunities:** The research might identify areas where increased collaboration between different stakeholders could lead to more effective standardisation processes.

For the General Public:

- ▶ **Awareness and Understanding:** The general public stands to gain a clearer understanding of how ICT standardisation impacts their daily lives, from the devices they use to the services they access.
- ▶ **Consumer Rights and Protections:** Insights from the research could highlight areas where consumer rights might be affected, leading to potential recommendations for enhanced protections.

In conclusion, the research team hopes to shed light on the intricate web of ICT standardisation, its evolving nature, and its implications for Europe. The anticipated findings aim to serve as a valuable resource for all parties involved, fostering informed discussions and decisions in the realm of ICT.

In the meantime, the team is eager to get feedback from readers on this policy paper, in order to not miss any important aspects worthy of our research's attention.

The StandICT.eu 2026 project is funded by the European Union under grant agreement no. 101091933.